

GENERAL CHARACTERISTICS OF TRAINING FOR CERTAIN TYPES
OF TRANSLATION

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Annotation: *At the moment, translation training is a very complex type of activity. To understand it, we studied the general principles of organizing translation training, determined what the professional competence of a translator and a translation teacher consists of, reviewed the content of translation training, studied translation exercises, and gave a general description of the types of translation. Now this is a very relevant issue, because due to such a phenomenon as integration in various areas of our life, there is a huge demand for professional translators who can convey and convey the whole meaning of what is said or written.*

Key words: *Professional competence, complex, process of learning, types of translation, lexical, semantic content, educational material, general principles, specific methods, original.*

Before studying the characteristics of translation training, you should consider the types of translation, since the process of learning translation usually raises the question of how much translation can deviate from the form of expression of the original. In this regard, we should distinguish between three types of translation:

Word-by-word translation. This is a mechanical translation of words of a foreign text in the order in which they occur in the text, without taking into account their syntactic and logical connections. Such a translation most often leads to nonsense and should be resolutely banished from practice, for example: Ann came

too late, to begin with. - Ann came too late to start with, instead of the correct one: Start with Ann coming too late.

A literal translation, if the idea of the translated text is correctly conveyed, tends to reproduce the syntactic structure and lexical composition of the original text as closely as possible. In cases where the syntactic structure of the translated sentence can be expressed by similar means in the translation, the literal translation can be considered as the final version of the translation without further literary processing, for example: The substance was dissolved in ether. The substance was dissolved in ether. However, such a coincidence of syntactic means in two languages is relatively rare. There are three ways to transfer lexical units during translation:

- ❖ using equivalents, i.e. direct correspondences that do not depend on the context.
- ❖ using analogs, i.e. synonymous words that are most relevant to the context.
- ❖ by descriptive translation, i.e. free transmission of the semantic content of the translated word or phrase.

Translation by ear - consecutive translation of individual phrases and small paragraphs. Conditions of implementation: the speaker (s) pronounces one or more related phrases and pauses, after which the translator agrees on the translation of what was heard for the participant or participants in the communication who do not speak the original language.

Factors that complicate the task:

- ❖ features of the speaker's speech (too fast tempo, unclear diction, accent, incorrect speech);
- ❖ a possible increase in the volume of the translated segment when the speaker failed and did not want to pause in a timely manner;
- ❖ use of hard-to-hear units in the speaker's speech that cannot be deduced from the context — names, dates, numbers, etc. (precision vocabulary).

Conditions for implementation: a conversation between two or more participants who speak their native languages. The translator translates relatively short statements in one language or another.

Factors that complicate the task:

- ❖ careless speech in conditions of personal contact with people who speak the same language;
- ❖ short, unfinished remarks designed for special knowledge of the interlocutor;
- ❖ simultaneous comments made by several people.
- ❖ an awkward position of the interpreter, which prevents him from seeing and hearing well some of the participants in the conversation.
- ❖ Factors that make this task easier:
- ❖ direct participation of the translator in the conversation, which makes it possible to clarify what was said and correct the translation;
- ❖ the opportunity to get acquainted in advance with the topic of the conversation and with the positions of its participants.

In the process of teaching translation, we should study not the methods of translating the educational material used, but methods of solving typical translation problems and strategies for finding individual creative solutions. In this sense, translation training involves the ability to identify typical translation tasks in the educational material and formulate general principles and specific methods for solving them.

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